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Review Article

A Review of Metformin and Spironolactone in Combined Dosage Form for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome with Emphasis on Pharmaceutical Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine–metabolic disorder marked by insulin resistance, hyperandrogenism, and ovulatory dysfunction, resulting in menstrual irregularities, infertility, and increased metabolic risk. Metformin improves insulin sensitivity and reduces hepatic glucose production, thereby indirectly decreasing androgen levels and improving metabolic and reproductive function. Spironolactone, owing to its antiandrogenic activity, is effective in controlling symptoms such as hirsutism and acne. Their combined use provides a rational therapeutic strategy by addressing both metabolic and hormonal abnormalities of PCOS. In addition to clinical management, accurate pharmaceutical analysis is essential to ensure drug quality, safety, and efficacy. Analytical techniques including RP-HPLC, UV spectrophotometry, and HPTLC are widely employed for method development, validation, and stability studies of these drugs. This review summarizes the pathophysiology, treatment approach, and analytical evaluation of metformin and spironolactone in PCOS.

INTRODUCTION

PCOS (Polycystic ovary syndrome): ^[1,2]

Polycystic ovary syndrome is a common metabolic and reproductive disorder characterized variably by high levels of androgens, insulin resistance, and ovulatory dysfunction, with not all patients affected by these three parameters. These alterations show up as oligomenorrhea or

amenorrhea, structural characteristics of polycystic ovaries on ultrasonography, and hyperandrogenism (hirsutism, acne, or scalp hair loss, or a combination of these). Polycystic ovarian syndrome, which has long been recognized as a reproductive issue, is now known to be a metabolic disorder linked to long-term health hazards, such as cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes.

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Worldwide, a large number of women of reproductive age suffer with the diverse endocrine condition known as polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS). Excess androgen levels, insulin resistance, oversized and dysfunctional ovaries, and other conditions are frequently linked to this

syndrome. According to estimates, over 10% of women get PCOS before to menopause and deal with its aftereffects.

Pathophysiology ^[3,4]:

Figure-1: Pathophysiology of PCOS.

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) develops mainly because of a disturbance in insulin action and reproductive hormone balance. In many women with PCOS, body tissues such as the liver and muscles do not respond effectively to insulin, so the pancreas produces higher levels of insulin to keep blood sugar normal. This excess insulin directly stimulates the ovaries to produce more androgens (male-type hormones). Elevated androgen levels interfere with the normal development and maturation of ovarian follicles, which prevents regular ovulation. At the same time, hormonal signaling from the brain becomes altered, resulting in an imbalance between luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), further disturbing ovarian function. Because of these changes, ovulation becomes irregular or may stop completely, menstrual cycles become abnormal, and immature follicles accumulate in the ovaries. These hormonal disturbances also worsen insulin resistance, creating a continuous cycle in which

metabolic and hormonal abnormalities reinforce each other. Thus, PCOS is a self-maintaining disorder where insulin resistance and excess androgen production together lead to reproductive and metabolic complications.

Causes of PCOS:

- Hormonal imbalance: the body makes more *androgens* (male-type hormones) than normal.
- Insulin resistance: insulin does not work properly, which increases hormone imbalance.
- Genetic factor: it can run in families.
- Unhealthy lifestyle: lack of exercise and weight gain can worsen the condition.

Treatment of PCOS:

- Healthy diet: balanced food with less sugar and refined carbs.

- Regular exercise: helps control weight and improves insulin action.
- Medicines: to regulate periods, reduce androgen levels, and improve fertility (as advised by a doctor).
- Weight management: even small weight loss can improve symptoms.

Introduction to Drug: ^[5,6]

METFORMIN: ^[5]

The FDA approved **METFORMIN** in 1995.

Metformin acts mainly as an insulin sensitizer by reducing hepatic glucose production, enhancing insulin sensitivity, and lowering circulating insulin levels. This reduction in hyperinsulinemia indirectly decreases ovarian androgen production, improving menstrual regularity and metabolic function.

Metformin mainly works by lowering blood sugar without increasing insulin release. It reduces glucose production in the liver, so less sugar enters the blood. It improves insulin sensitivity, helping body cells use glucose more effectively. It slows glucose absorption from the intestine, which prevents sudden sugar spikes after meals.

SPIRONOLACTONE: ^[6]

The FDA approve **SPIRONOLACTONE** in 1960.

Spirolactone is a potassium-sparing diuretic and aldosterone antagonist used to treat conditions such as hypertension, heart failure, edema, and primary hyperaldosteronism. It blocks aldosterone receptors in the distal renal tubules of the kidney, promoting sodium and water excretion while sparing potassium. Besides its diuretic effect,

spironolactone exhibits antiandrogenic properties, making it effective in treating androgen-related disorders like hirsutism, acne, and polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Its diverse actions contribute to cardiovascular and hormonal disease management. Research supports its role in improving fluid balance and reducing blood pressure alongside other therapies.

Rationale of the work:

Metformin is a first-line antidiabetic agent, while Spironolactone is a potassium-sparing diuretic used for conditions such as hypertension and PCOS. Combination therapy involving these drugs may offer improved management of metabolic disorders such as insulin resistance with cardiovascular complications.

The combination of metformin plus spironolactone is rational in PCOS because it targets dual pathophysiology: insulin resistance via metformin and androgen excess via spironolactone. The registered trial NCT03981861 specifically tests metformin (500 mg BID) + spironolactone (50 mg QD) over 6 months in adolescents with PCOS to evaluate metabolic and neuroendocrine outcomes. Published clinical data and meta-analysis support that the combo more effectively lowers BMI and total testosterone, and improves glucose / insulin indices more than metformin alone, without significant increase in adverse events. However, risks include hyperkalemia, worsening renal load, and potential interaction altering glycemic control; thus, careful patient selection, baseline labs, and periodic monitoring are crucial.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Literature review of Metformin:

Table 1: Literature review of Metformin

Sr. No.	Title	Method	Description	Ref No.
1	Indian Pharmacopoeia Volume-II	IP	Mobile phase: Solution Containing 0.087 percent w/v of Sodium chloride, adjusted to pH 3.5 using 1%v/v solution of Orthophosphoric acid Stationary phase: A stainless-steel column (30 cm × 4 mm, 10 μm) packed with octadecylsilane bonded to silica Wavelength: 218 nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	7
2	British Pharmacopoeia Volume-II	BP	Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: 0.05 M KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH 3.5): acetonitrile (84:16 % v/v) Stationary phase: Stainless steel column (12.5 cm × 4.5 cm, 5 μm) packed with strong cation-exchange silica gel (or Luna SCX) Wavelength: 218 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	8
3	United Stat Pharmacopoeia- National Formulary Volume-III	USP	Mobile phase: Prepare solution in water, containing 17 g of monobasic ammonium phosphate per L, adjust with phosphoric acid to pH of 3.0 and mix Stationary phase: 3.9 mm × 30 cm, 10 μm packing, L1 Wavelength: 218 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	9
4	Development and Validation of UV Spectroscopic Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Metformin HCl in Pure and Its Marketed Tablets	UV	Solvent: Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water = 1:1:1 λ max: 298 nm Linearity: 1-50 μg/mL	10
5	Quantitative UV-Spectrophotometric Method for the Analysis of Teneligliptin HBr and Metformin HCl in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	UV	Solvent: 0.1 N Sulfuric acid λ max: 220 nm for (Metformin HCl) and 240 nm for (Teneligliptin HBr) Linearity: 100 μg/ml	11
6	Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Sitagliptin and Metformin in Bulk & Combined Formulation	UV	Solvent: Distilled water λ max: 237 nm for (Metformin) and 267 nm for (Sitagliptin) Linearity: 4-14 μg/mL for (Metformin) and 10-300 μg/ml for (Sitagliptin)	12
7	Development and Validation of Green UV Derivative Spectrophotometric Methods for Simultaneous Determination of Metformin and Remogliflozin	UV	Solvent: Water λ max: 252.2 nm for (Metformin) and 233.0 nm for (Remogliflozin)	13

			Linearity: 2.5-35 µg/mL for (Metformin) and 1-20 µg/ml for (Remogliflozin)	
8	Spectrophotometric Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Anagliptin and Metformin HCl by Q-Absorption Ratio Method in Synthetic Mixture	UV	Solvent: Distilled Water λ max: 233 nm for (Metformin) and 238 nm for (Anagliptin) Linearity: 5-30 µg/mL for (Metformin) and 2-12 µg/mL for (Anagliptin)	14
9	Method Development, Validation & Stress Studies of Dapagliflozin and Metformin Hydrochloride Using UV-Vis Spectroscopy	UV	Solvent: Water as diluent λ max: 232 nm for (Metformin) and 222 nm for (Dapagliflozin) Linearity: 1–20µg/ml for (Metformin) and 2 – 32µg/ml for (Dapagliflozin)	15
10	Simultaneous Assays of Metformin HCl and Glibenclamide Mixture Using Spectrophotometry Methods	UV	Solvent: Water λ max: 230-240 nm for (Metformin) and 225-235 nm for (Glibenclamide) Linearity: linearity = 0.9881 for (Metformin) and linearity = 0.9993 for (Glibenclamide)	16
11	Development and Validation of UV-Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Metformin HCl and Pioglitazone in Tablet Dosage Form	UV	Solvent: Methanol λ max: 232.4 nm and 241.8 nm for (Metformin) and 264.8 nm and 272.8 nm for (Pioglitazone) Linearity: 5-40 µg/mL	17
12	Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride by UV-Spectroscopic Area Under Curve Method	UV	Solvent: Distilled water λ max: 221-241 nm Linearity: 5-25 µg/mL	18
13	Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin HCl and Repaglinide in Pharmaceutical Formulation	UV	Solvent: Methanol λ max: 238 nm for (Metformin HCL) and 294 nm for (Repaglinide) Linearity: 2-100 µg/mL for (Metformin) and 1-35 µg/ml for (Repaglinide)	19
14	Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Metformin in Bulk & Tablet Dosage Form	UV	Solvent: Water λ max: 234 nm Linearity: 10-50 µg/mL	20
15	Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride by UV Spectrophotometric Method in Pharmaceutical Formulation	UV	Solvent: Distilled water λ max: 232 nm Linearity: 2-10 µg/mL	21
16	A novel RP-HPLC approach for simultaneous determination of Dapagliflozin, Linagliptin, and Metformin in pharmaceutical formulations	HPLC	Mobile phase: Acetonitrile / Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) = (40:60%v/v) Stationary phase: Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) Wavelength: 230 nm Flow rate: 0.80 ml/min	22

17	Development and Validation of HPLC Method for the Estimation of Metformin HCl and Anagliptin in its Synthetic Mixture	HPLC	Mobile phase: Buffer: Acetonitrile = (80:20%v/v) (pH 3.0) Stationary phase: C ₁₈ (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 232 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	23
18	Analytical method of development and validation for determination of Canagliflozin and Metformin in API and synthetic mixture by RP-HPLC	HPLC	Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (pH 3.5) = (70:30%v/v) Stationary phase: C ₁₈ column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 254 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	24
19	Development And Validation Of RP-HPLC Method For Anagliptin and Metformin Hydrochloride and Its Related Impurities In Tablet Dosage Form	HPLC	Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: 0.05 M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) = (50 :50 %v/v) Stationary phase: Kromasil C ₁₈ column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 220 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	25
20	Stability Indicating Assay Method of Metformin, Linagliptin and Empagliflozin in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by HPLC Method	HPLC	Mobile phase: Water: Acetonitrile (65:35% v/v) Stationary phase: C18 column (4.6 mm × 25 cm; 5 μm) Wavelength: 269 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	26
21	Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Imeglimin and Metformin	HPLC	Mobile phase: Water: Acetonitrile = (50:50%v/v) Stationary phase: Hypersil C18 (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 244 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	27
22	Analytical quality-by-design approach for development and validation of HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Omarigliptin, Metformin, and Ezetimibe	HPLC	Mobile phase: Methanol: 6.6 mM KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH 7) = (67 :33% v/v) Stationary phase: Hypersil BDS C18 column Wavelength: 235 nm Flow rate: 0.814 ml/min	28
23	A novel RP-HPLC method development and validation for the quantification of a potential anti-diabetic drug Metformin Hydrochloride in tablet dosage form.	HPLC	Mobile phase: Buffer (Tetra-Butyl Ammonium Hydroxide 0.002 %) : Acetonitrile (70:30 % v/v) Stationary phase: Shimadzu Shim-pack GIST C ₁₈ (5 μm × 4.6 × 250 mm) Wavelength: 232 nm Flow rate: 0.50 ml/min	29
24	Impurity profiling method development and validation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Teneigliptin Hydrobromide hydrate in their combination tablet dosage form by using RP-HPLC with UV/PDA detector	HPLC	Mobile phase: Mobile Phase A: (pH 3.0) Buffer Mobile Phase B: Methanol Stationary phase: BDS Hypersil C ₁₈ (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	30

			Wavelength: 210 nm Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	
25	Development and validation of stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of Ertugliflozin pidolate and Metformin HCl in bulk and tablets	HPLC	Mobile phase: 0.1% ortho-phosphoric acid buffer (pH 2.7) : Acetonitrile = (65:35% v/v) Stationary phase: Kromasil C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 224 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	31
26	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Glipizide in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	HPLC	Mobile phase: Methanol: Water = (60:40%v/v) Stationary phase: Cosmosil C ₁₈ (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 220 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	32
27	Development and validation of a new analytical HPLC method for simultaneous determination of the antidiabetic drugs, metformin and gliclazide.	HPLC	Mobile phase: ammonium formate buffer (pH 3.5): acetonitrile (45:55% v/v) Stationary phase: Alltima CN (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) Wavelength: 227 nm Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min	33
28	Development of new validated HPTLC Method for simultaneous estimation of Canagliflozin and Metformin in Tablet Formulation	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Toluene: Methanol: Triethylamine: Glacial Acetic Acid = (7: 2.6: 0.2: 0.2 %v/v/v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎ aluminium sheet λ max: 254 nm Concentration range: 250–2500 ng / band for Metformin, 75-750ng/band of Canagliflozin	34
29	A Sensitive HPTLC Method for the Estimation of Glibenclamide, Rosiglitazone Maleate and Metformin Hydrochloride from a Multicomponent Dosage Form	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Methanol: Tetrahydrofuran: Water: Glacial Acetic Acid = (16: 3.6: 4: 0.4% v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated RP-18 F _{254s} aluminum sheets λ max: 214 nm Concentration range: 120–600 ng / band for Metformin 200–1000 ng / band for Glibenclamide 200–1000 ng / band for Rosiglitazone Maleate	35
30	A Novel Validated Stability-Indicating Analytical Method for Simultaneous Quantification of Metformin Hydrochloride and Empagliflozin by HPTLC	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: 2% Ammonium acetate: Isopropyl alcohol: Triethylamine = (4: 6: 0.1 %v/v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎ plates (10×10 cm, 0.2 mm) λ max: 242 nm Concentration range:	36

			5000–30,000 ng / band for Metformin 125–750 ng /band for Empagliflozin	
31	HPTLC – Stability Indicating Densitometric Method for Determination of Metformin Hydrochloride in Tablet Formulation	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: water: methanol: triethylamine (1:3.5:0.2 %v/v) Stationary phase: silica gel 60F-254 λ max: 247 nm Concentration range: 100–600 ng /band	37
32	Development and Validation Stability-Indicating HPTLC Method for Determination of Vildagliptin and Metformin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Methanol: Acetonitrile: Glacial Acetic Acid = (2: 3.5: 2.5: 0.2%v/v/v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎ HPTLC plate λ max: 217 nm Concentration range: 500 ng/band for Metformin 100 ng/band for Vildagliptin	38
33	Development & Validation of Stability-Indicating HPTLC Method for Metformin Hydrochloride & Benfotiamine in Bulk and Combined Dosage Form	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Benzene: Methanol: Triethylamine = (8.5: 1: 0.5% v/v/v) Stationary phase: Silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎ aluminium TLC-sheet λ max: 249 nm Concentration range: 500–3000 ng / band for Metformin 75-450 ng / band for Benfotiamine	39
34	HPTLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin HCl and Sitagliptin in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Ammonium sulphate (0.5%): 2-Propanol: Methanol = (8: 1.6: 1.6%v/v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎ plate λ max: 254 nm Concentration range: 7-15µg/spot for Metformin 700-1500 ng/spot for Sitagliptin	40

Literature review of Spironolactone:

Table 2 : Literature review of Spironolactone

Sr. No.	Title	Method	Description	Ref No.
1	Zero-order and first-derivative spectrophotometry for the determination of Spironolactone in pharmaceutical tablets	UV	Solvent: Methanol λ max: 239 nm (zero-order) & 250.4 nm (1st derivative) Linearity: 6.0-20.0 µg/mL	41
2	Analysis of spironolactone in compound powder by ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometry	UV	Solvent: Methanol (blank) λ max: 238 nm Linearity: 5-30 µg/mL	42

3	Development and validation of combined dosage form of Torseimide and Spironolactone in Ultra-violet spectroscopy by simultaneous equation method	UV	Solvent: 50% v/v methanol in distilled water λ max: 288 nm Linearity: 5-25 μ g/mL for Spironolactone, 1-5 μ g/ml for Torseimide	43
4	Quantification of Spironolactone by first and second order UV Derivative Spectrophotometry in bulk and tablet dosage form	UV	Solvent: Methanol λ max: 226 nm (1st-derivative) & 262 nm (2nd-derivative) Linearity: 5-35 μ g/mL	44
5	Method development and its validation for estimation of Spironolactone in tablet dosage form by UV spectrophotometry	UV	Solvent: 50% v/v methanol in distilled water λ max: 238 nm Linearity: 2-24 μ g/mL	45
6	Simultaneous estimation of Metolazone and Spironolactone in combined tablet dosage form by UV spectroscopy	UV	Solvent: 50% v/v methanol in distilled water λ max: 242.5 nm for Spironolactone, 345 nm for Metolazone Linearity: 5-25 μ g/ml for Spironolactone, 0.5 -2.5 μ g/ml for Metolazone	46
7	A New Analytical Method Development and Validation for Quantitative Estimation of Spironolactone and Furosemide in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form by Using RP-HPLC	HPLC	Mobile phase: Methanol: TEA buffer pH 4.2 (40:60% v/v) Stationary phase: Symmetry C18, 4.6 \times 150 mm, 5 μ m Wavelength: 272 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	47
8	Analytical Method Development and Validation of Spironolactone by RP-HPLC Method	HPLC	Mobile phase: 10 mM KH ₂ PO ₄ + 1% TEA (pH 4.5) : Acetonitrile (50:50%v/v) Stationary phase: Hypersil BDS C18, 150 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m Wavelength: 226 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	48
9	Development And Validation of A RP - HPLC Method For The Simultaneous Determination of Spironolactone and Hydrochlorothiazide	HPLC	Mobile phase: Methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 4.8 (55:45% v/v) Stationary phase: Inertsil C18, 4.6 \times 250mm, 5 μ m Wavelength: 282 nm Flow rate: 1 ml/min	49
10	HPLC – Quality by Design Approach for Simultaneous Detection of Torseimide, Spironolactone and Their Degradant Impurities.	HPLC	Mobile phase: Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water (5:3:2% v/v/v) Stationary phase: Inertsil ODS-3 C18 (150 \times 4.6 mm, 3 μ m) Wavelength: 254 nm Flow rate: 0.2 ml/min	50

11	Development and validation of HPTLC and green HPLC methods for determination of furosemide, spironolactone and canrenone, in pure forms, tablets and spiked human plasma	HPLC	<p>Mobile phase: Ethanol: Deionized water (45:55% v/v), pH 3.5</p> <p>Stationary phase: C18 (4.6×100 mm)</p> <p>Wavelength: 254 nm</p> <p>Flow rate: 1 ml/min</p>	51
12	Development and Validation of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography Assay Method of Spironolactone	HPLC	<p>Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer pH 4: Acetonitrile (1:1%v/v)</p> <p>Stationary phase: C18 Inertsil, 250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm</p> <p>Wavelength: 240 nm</p> <p>Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min</p>	52
13	Development and Validation of a Stability-Indicating HPLC Assay Method for Simultaneous Determination of Spironolactone and Furosemide	HPLC	<p>Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: Ammonium acetate buffer (50:50 %v/v)</p> <p>Stationary phase: Wakosil II 5C8RS, 150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm</p> <p>Wavelength: 254 nm</p> <p>Flow rate: 1 ml/min</p>	53
14	Simultaneous Estimation of Furosemide and Spironolactone in Combined Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by RP-HPLC	HPLC	<p>Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: Water</p> <p>Stationary phase: Hiber C18, 250 × 4.6mm, 5 μm</p> <p>Wavelength: 237 nm</p> <p>Flow rate: 1 ml/min</p>	54
15	Stability-Indicating HPTLC Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Spironolactone and Hydrochlorothiazide in Bulk and Tablet	HPTLC	<p>Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water = (3:7% v/v)</p> <p>Stationary phase: Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ HPTLC plate</p> <p>λ max: 270 nm</p> <p>Concentration range: 100–600 μg/mL for spironolactone 50-300 μg/mL for Hydrochlorothiazide</p>	55
16	Development and Validation of HPTLC SIAM for Furosemide and Spironolactone	HPLC	<p>Mobile Phase: Chloroform: Methanol: Glacial Acetic Acid = (7.5: 2: 0.5% v/v/v)</p> <p>Stationary phase: Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (HPTLC, aluminium)</p> <p>λ max: 234 nm</p> <p>Concentration range: 1000 ng/band for spironolactone 400 ng/band for Furosemide</p>	56
17	Development and validation of HPTLC and green HPLC methods for determination of furosemide, spironolactone and canrenone, in pure forms, tablets and spiked human plasma	HPLC	<p>Mobile Phase: Ethyl acetate: Triethylamine: Acetic acid = (9: 0.7: 0.5% v/v/v)</p> <p>Stationary phase: Silica gel HPTLC F₂₅₄ plates</p>	57

			<p>λ max: 254 nm Concentration range: 0.05–2.6 μg / band for spironolactone 0.2-2 μg / band for furosemide 0.05-2 μg / band for canrenone</p>	
18	Development and Validation of HPTLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metolazone and Spironolactone in Bulk Drug and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	HPLC	<p>Mobile Phase: n-Propanol: Triethylamine = (7: 3 %v/v) Stationary phase: Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (Merck aluminium plate) λ max: 240 nm Concentration range: 300–700 ng / spot for spironolactone 300 -700 ng/spot for Metolazone</p>	58
19	Development and validation of a HPTLC method for simultaneous determination of furosemide and spironolactone in its tablet formulation	HPLC	<p>Mobile Phase: Ethyl acetate: Hexane = (80:20% v/v) Stationary phase: Pre-coated silica gel GF₂₅₄ (aluminium) λ max: 254 nm Concentration range: 0.040-0.160 mg /ml for spironolactone 0.016-0.064 mg /ml for furosemide</p>	59

CONCLUSION:

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a multifactorial endocrine disorder mainly driven by insulin resistance and hyperandrogenism. Metformin improves insulin sensitivity and metabolic function, while spironolactone effectively reduces androgen-related symptoms. Their combination provides a rational and more effective approach by targeting both metabolic and hormonal abnormalities of PCOS. Clinical evidence supports improved outcomes in terms of body weight, insulin indices, and androgen levels with combination therapy compared to monotherapy. Accurate pharmaceutical analysis is essential for ensuring drug quality and safety. In conclusion, an integrated therapeutic strategy combining metformin and spironolactone, supported by validated analytical methodologies such as RP-HPLC, offers a comprehensive

approach to the effective management and pharmaceutical evaluation of PCOS. Continued research focusing on optimized combination therapy and advanced analytical techniques will further enhance treatment outcomes and ensure drug quality, safety, and efficacy in clinical practice.

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